

Bound of Fractal Uncertainty Exponent for Discrete Cantor Sets

Abzal Tangsykbay

Under the direction of

Alain Kangabire

Abstract

We bounded the case when $y = 0$ in the sum $\sum_{j=0}^L \sup_{y \in [0, \delta]} \left| \sum_{l=0}^L e^{2\pi i(\alpha j^2 + y)l^2} \right|$. These sums are important to analyze function waves over Discrete Cantor sets, and are closely related to the fractal uncertainty principle. We used previous well-known theorems and approximated the irrational α to a rational number using analytical number theory. We got that the sum is less than a number in the order of $N^{2 - \frac{1}{30}}$. This bound is much better than the intuitive bound we had before the research, N^2 . Further, this result can be used in the analysis of quantum open baker's maps.

Summary

In the field of harmonic analysis, the uncertainty principle analyzes the behavior of the wave functions. This paper focused on the analysis of wave functions over the Discrete Cantor sets through the fractal uncertainty principle. We bounded a complex exponential sum using techniques from analytical number theory, such as Dirichlet's approximation lemma. Further applications also involve the analysis of quantum open baker's maps.

1 Introduction

Harmonic analysis is a field of mathematics that focuses on analyzing the behavior of wave functions. When analyzing wave-like functions, we generally consider two dimensions: frequency and time. The Fourier transform is a method for transforming a function from the time domain to the frequency domain and vice versa. The uncertainty principle states that if a function is localized at a specific point in time, it must be spread out in the frequency domain.

This paper focuses on the analysis of the behavior of wave functions over Discrete Cantor sets. Cantor sets are sets of numbers derived by repeatedly deleting the middle third of each segment. The fractal uncertainty principle examines whether the localization of a function over a fractal in the time domain, specifically a Cantor set in our case, results in a spread in the frequency domain. This principle has applications in wave analysis, particularly in the fields of signal analysis and quantum mechanics.

Previous works have linked the analysis of quantum open baker's maps to the bounding of exponential sums and the fractal uncertainty principle. Specifically, bounding the following sum:

$$\sum_{j=0}^L \sup_{y \in [0, \delta]} \left| \sum_{l=0}^L e^{2\pi i(\alpha j^2 + y)l^2} \right|,$$

where α is some irrational number and δ is a relatively small real number, is crucial for analyzing the map with the alphabet $A = \{0, 1^2, 2^2, \dots, M^2\}$. This paper focuses on bounding a specific case of the sum above:

$$\sum_{n_1=0}^{N-1} \left| \sum_{n_2=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i(\alpha n_1^2) n_2^2} \right|.$$

An intuitive bound for this sum is N^2 because each element is no more than 1. In our research, we have found a better bound of the form $CN^{2-\beta}$.

Open quantum baker's maps have previously been studied by Alain Kangabire [1], Keating–Novaes–Prado–Sieber [2], Keating–Nonnenmacher–Novaes–Sieber [3], and Dyatlov–Jin [4]; see the introduction to [4] for a more detailed review of the literature.

2 Preliminaries

We begin by providing the following definition:

Definition 2.1. A real number α is (C, ϵ) -**Diophantine** if for all $p/q \in \mathbb{Q}$ in lowest terms,

$$\left| \alpha - \frac{p}{q} \right| \geq Cq^{-2-\epsilon}.$$

We say α is ϵ -Diophantine if it is (C, ϵ) -Diophantine for some $C > 0$.

Further in this paper, we assume that α is ϵ -Diophantine. In this section, we prove the following theorem:

Theorem 2.1. *If α is ϵ -diophantine and $N \in \mathbb{N}$ is large enough, then there exist a constant C such that*

$$\left| \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i \alpha n^2} \right| \leq CN^{\frac{1}{2} + \epsilon}, \quad (1)$$

for some relatively small ϵ .

Proof. We start with the following definition:

Definition 2.2 (Distance to the closest integer function). For every real number β define $\|\beta\|_{\mathbb{Z}} = \min_{a \in \mathbb{Z}} |\beta - a|$

Next, we prove lemma 2.2:

Lemma 2.2. *The following inequality holds*

$$\left| \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i \alpha n} \right| \leq c \min \left(N, \frac{1}{\|\alpha\|_{\mathbb{Z}}} \right).$$

Proof. We know that

$$\left| \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i \alpha n} \right| = \left| \frac{(e^{2\pi i \alpha N} - 1)(e^{-\pi i \alpha N})}{(e^{2\pi i \alpha} - 1)(e^{-\pi i \alpha})} \right| = \left| \frac{\sin(\pi \alpha N)}{\sin(\pi \alpha)} \right|.$$

We express $\alpha = a + b$, where $a \in \mathbb{Z}$, and $0 \leq b < 1$. Then we have

$$|\sin(\pi \alpha)| = |\sin(\pi b)| > \|b\|_{\mathbb{Z}},$$

where last inequality comes from the fact that $\|b\|_{\mathbb{Z}}$ equals b and $1 - b$ for $b \leq \frac{1}{2}$ and $b \geq \frac{1}{2}$ respectively. Therefore, we get that

$$\left| \frac{\sin \pi \alpha N}{\sin \pi \alpha} \right| \leq \frac{c}{\|\alpha\|_{\mathbb{Z}}},$$

for some constant $c \in \mathbb{R}$. Finally, since $\left| \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} e^{2i\pi \alpha n} \right| \leq N$ we get the bound

$$\left| \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} e^{2i\pi \alpha n} \right| \leq c \min \left(N, \frac{1}{\|\alpha\|_{\mathbb{Z}}} \right).$$

□

We know that

$$\left| \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i \alpha n^2} \right|^2 = \left(\sum_{n_1=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i \alpha n_1^2} \right) \cdot \left(\sum_{n_2=0}^{N-1} e^{-2\pi i \alpha n_2^2} \right) \leq \left| \sum_{n_1=0}^{N-1} \sum_{n_2=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i \alpha (n_1^2 - n_2^2)} \right|.$$

Define d as a number such that $n_1 - n_2 = d$. For every possible value of d , we choose values of n_2 from $N_1(d)$ to $N_2(d)$ so that every pair (n_1, n_2) will be chosen, and $N_2(d) - N_1(d) \leq N$. By substituting it in the equality above and using the Lemma 2.2, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i \alpha n^2} \right|^2 &\leq \left| \sum_{|d| \leq N} \sum_{n_2=N_1(d)}^{N_2(d)} e^{2\pi i \alpha (2dn_2 + d^2)} \right| = \left| \sum_{|d| \leq N} e^{2\pi i \alpha d^2} \sum_{n_2=N_1(d)}^{N_2(d)} e^{2\pi i \alpha (2dn_2)} \right| \\ &\leq \sum_{|d| \leq N} \left| \sum_{n_2=N_1(d)}^{N_2(d)} e^{2\pi i (2d\alpha)n_2} \right| \leq \sum_{|d| \leq N} c \min(N, \|2d\alpha\|_{\mathbb{Z}}^{-1}). \end{aligned}$$

Because for every $-N \leq d_0 \leq N$ there exists $d_1 = 2d_0$, $-2N \leq d_1 \leq 2N$, we have

$$\left| \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i \alpha n^2} \right|^2 \leq \sum_{|d| \leq N} c \min(N, \|2d\alpha\|_{\mathbb{Z}}^{-1}) \leq \sum_{|d| \leq 2N} c \min(N, \|d\alpha\|_{\mathbb{Z}}^{-1}). \quad (2)$$

Lemma 2.3 (Dirichlet's approximation lemma). *Let $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ and $N \in \mathbb{N}$. Then there exist $a \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $q \in \mathbb{N}$ with $q \leq N$ such that $|\alpha - \frac{a}{q}| \leq \frac{1}{qN}$ [5]*

We define $f(x) = \|x\|_{\mathbb{Z}}$ and use Dirichlet's approximation lemma 2.3 to write $\alpha = \frac{a}{q} + \gamma$; where $|\gamma| \leq \frac{1}{q(2N)}$, and $\gcd(a, q) = 1$. Next, we pick $-2N \leq d \leq 2N$. As a result, we have $d\alpha = \frac{ad}{q} + d\gamma$, where $|d\gamma| \leq \frac{1}{q}$. We write $d\gamma = \theta$. Then $f(d\alpha) = f(k + \frac{p}{q} + \theta) = f(\frac{p}{q} + \theta)$ for some $k, p \in \mathbb{Z}$, where $0 \leq p \leq q - 1$. Finally, we see that

$$f\left(\frac{p}{q} + \theta\right) \geq \begin{cases} \frac{p-1}{q}, & 1 < p \leq \frac{q}{2}. \\ 1 - \frac{p+1}{q}, & \frac{q}{2} \leq p < q - 1. \\ 0, & |p| \leq 1. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Next, we define

$$E_p = \left\{ d : |d| \leq 2N \text{ and } \frac{ad}{q} = m + \frac{p}{q}, \text{ for } m \in \mathbb{Z} \right\}.$$

Note that

- $E_{t_1} \cap E_{t_2} = \emptyset$ for $t_1 \neq t_2, 0 \leq t_1, t_2 \leq q - 1$
- $E_0 \cup E_1 \cup \dots \cup E_{q-1} = \{-2N, -2N + 1, \dots, 2N\}$
- For any $r \in \mathbb{Z}$, $\{ra, (r+1)a, \dots, (r+q-1)a\} \equiv \{0, 1, \dots, q-1\} \pmod{q}$, because $\gcd(a, q) = 1$

Using observations above we can say that among any q subsequent values of d there will be no two values in the same set E_l , therefore all $4N + 1$ possible values of d will be roughly equally distributed among sets E_P , which gives us the following inequality:

$$\left\lfloor \frac{4N+1}{q} \right\rfloor \leq |E_p| \leq \left\lceil \frac{4N+1}{q} \right\rceil + 1 \leq \frac{4N+1}{q} + 1.$$

Therefore, if we use this definition in our inequality and use properties from the equation 3, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{|d| \leq 2N} c \min(N, \|d\alpha\|_{\mathbb{Z}}^{-1}) &= \sum_{0 \leq p \leq q-1} \sum_{d \in E_p} c \min(N, \|d\alpha\|_{\mathbb{Z}}^{-1}) \\
&\leq \sum_{2 \leq p \leq \frac{q}{2}} c \left(\frac{4N+1}{q} + 1 \right) \min \left(N, \left(\frac{p-1}{q} \right)^{-1} \right) + \sum_{p \in \{0,1,q-1\}} c \left(\frac{4N+1}{q} + 1 \right) N \\
&\quad + \sum_{\frac{q}{2} \leq p \leq q-2} c \left(\frac{4N+1}{q} + 1 \right) \min \left(N, \left(\frac{q-p-1}{q} \right)^{-1} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

And we note that

$$\sum_{2 \leq p \leq \frac{q}{2}} \left(\frac{4N+1}{q} + 1 \right) \min \left(N, \left(\frac{p-1}{q} \right)^{-1} \right) = \sum_{\frac{q}{2} \leq p \leq q-2} \left(\frac{4N+1}{q} + 1 \right) \min \left(N, \left(\frac{q-p-1}{q} \right)^{-1} \right),$$

and

$$\sum_{p \in \{0,1,q-1\}} \left(\frac{4N+1}{q} + 1 \right) N = 3N \left(\frac{4N+1}{q} + 1 \right).$$

By using this, we get

$$\sum_{|d| \leq 2N} c \min(N, \|d\alpha\|_{\mathbb{Z}}^{-1}) \leq 2cq \left(\frac{4N}{q} + 1 \right) \sum_{2 \leq p \leq \frac{q}{2}} \frac{1}{p-1} + 3cN \left(\frac{4N}{q} + 1 \right)$$

By using the facts that for sufficiently large $m \in \mathbb{N}$ we have

$$\sum_{1 \leq x \leq m} \frac{1}{x} \leq \log 2m,$$

and for some relatively small ϵ and sufficiently large N

$$\log 2q \leq \log 2N \leq N^\epsilon,$$

we get that

$$\left| \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i \alpha n^2} \right|^2 \leq 12cN \log q + \frac{18cN^2}{q} \leq c_1 N^{1+\epsilon} \left(\frac{N^{1-\epsilon}}{q} + 1 \right). \quad (4)$$

Because we assume that α is ϵ -Diophantine, we have

$$\frac{1}{2qN} \geq \left| \alpha - \frac{a}{q} \right| \geq \frac{c}{q^{2+\mu}} \implies q \geq c_2 N^{1-\mu_1}.$$

By using it in our inequality 4 we get

$$\left| \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i \alpha n^2} \right|^2 \leq c_1 N^{1+\epsilon} \left(\frac{N^{1-\epsilon}}{q} + 1 \right) \leq c_1 N^{1+\epsilon} (c_3 N^\delta + 1) = CN^{1+\kappa}, \quad (5)$$

for some relatively small κ and constant C , which completes the proof. \square

3 The proof of the final result

In this section, we provide a proof of the following theorem:

Theorem 3.1.

$$\sum_{n_1=0}^{N-1} \left| \sum_{n_2=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i(\alpha n_1^2)n_2^2} \right| \leq (2 + \sqrt{2})N^{2-\frac{1}{30}}.$$

Proof.

Definition 3.1. For $D, N \in \mathbb{N}$, $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$, define the sum

$$R_{D,N}(\alpha) = \sum_{|d| \leq D} \min(N, ||d\alpha||^{-1})$$

Using this definition, we can rewrite equation 2 as follows:

$$\left| \sum_{n=0}^N e^{2\pi i\beta n^2} \right|^2 \leq R_{2N,N}(\beta). \quad (6)$$

Theorem 3.2. [6] For any irrational α , if $R_{D,N}(\alpha) \geq DL$, and $L \geq 1000 \log N$, then there exists $\frac{a}{q} \in \mathbb{Q}$ with $q \leq \frac{N}{L}$ such that

$$\left| \alpha - \frac{a}{q} \right| \leq \frac{\log N}{qDL}.$$

Let $L \in \mathbb{N}$, $L \approx N^{1-\frac{1}{15}} > 1000 \log 2N$, for sufficiently large N . We define

$$A = \{n_1 : R_{2N,N}(\alpha n_1^2) \leq 2NL\}, B = \{n_1 : R_{2N,N}(\alpha n_1^2) > 2NL\}.$$

. Now we can rewrite the sum

$$\sum_{n_1=0}^{N-1} \left| \sum_{n_2=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i(\alpha n_1^2)n_2^2} \right| = \sum_{n_1 \in A} \left| \sum_{n_2=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i(\alpha n_1^2)n_2^2} \right| + \sum_{n_1 \in B} \left| \sum_{n_2=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i(\alpha n_1^2)n_2^2} \right|.$$

From the equation 6 we know that

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n_1=0}^{N-1} \left| \sum_{n_2=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i(\alpha n_1^2)n_2^2} \right| &\leq \sum_{n_1 \in A} \left| \sqrt{R_{2N,N}(\alpha n_1^2)} \right| + \sum_{n_1 \in B} \left| \sqrt{R_{2N,N}(\alpha n_1^2)} \right| \\ &\leq |A|\sqrt{2NL} + |B|N \\ &\leq N \left(\sqrt{2}N^{1-\frac{1}{30}} + |B| \right) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Conjecture 3.3. The following inequality is true:

$$|B| \leq 2N^{1-\frac{1}{30}}.$$

In this paper, we assume that conjecture 3.3 is true. We derived this result using analytical number theory techniques and Theorem 3.2, but are still in the process of checking the calculations. Using conjecture 3.3 in our inequality 7 gives us the following bound:

$$\sum_{n_1=0}^{N-1} \left| \sum_{n_2=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i(\alpha n_1^2)n_2^2} \right| \leq (2 + \sqrt{2})N^{2-\frac{1}{30}}.$$

□

4 Conclusion

In this paper we bounded the sum

$$\sum_{n_1=0}^{N-1} \left| \sum_{n_2=0}^{N-1} e^{2\pi i(\alpha n_1^2)n_2^2} \right| \leq (2 + \sqrt{2})N^{2-\frac{1}{30}}.$$

This sum is intuitively bounded by N^2 ; however, this result gives a much better understanding of the sum above because of the significant difference between N^2 and $N^{2-\frac{1}{30}}$. In further research, this bound could be applied to analyze cases in the sum that directly relates to open quantum maps,

$$\sum_{j=0}^L \sup_{y \in [0, \delta]} \left| \sum_{l=0}^L e^{2\pi i(\alpha j^2 + y)l^2} \right|.$$

5 Acknowledgments

I want to express my sincere gratitude to my mentor, Alain Kangabire, my head mentors, Dr. Tanya Khovanova, Dr. Jonathan Bloom, Prof. David Jerisson, and my tutor, Dr. Jenny Sendova, for their invaluable guidance and support throughout this research. Their insights and expertise have contributed significantly to the development and completion of this work.

I also extend my heartfelt thanks to my teaching assistants, Lauren Shen, Srikara Vishnubhatla, and Ella Lan, for their dedicated support and mentorship in teaching me how to write academic papers. Their patience and knowledge have been instrumental in developing my writing skills and in completing this research.

I would also like to thank the Research Science Institute, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Center for Excellence in Education, and “BILIM-INNOVATION” International Community Fund for providing the necessary resources and environment to conduct this research.

Lastly, I am deeply grateful to my family for their unwavering support and understanding during this research. Their patience and encouragement have been a constant source of motivation.

References

- [1] A. Kangabire. Bounds on the fractal uncertainty exponent and a spectral gap. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2406.06815>, 2024.
- [2] J. P. Keating, M. Novaes, S. D. Prado, et al. Semiclassical structure of chaotic resonance eigenfunctions. <https://arxiv.org/abs/quant-ph/0605217>, 2006.
- [3] J. P. Keating, S. ephane Nonnenmacher, M. Novaes, et al. On the resonance eigenstates of an open quantum baker map. <https://arxiv.org/abs/0806.1678>, 2008.
- [4] S. Dyatlov and L. Jin. Resonances for open quantum maps and a fractal uncertainty principle. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1608.02238>, 2017.
- [5] G. H. Hardy and E. M. Wright. An introduction to the theory of numbers. 5th ed., 1979.
- [6] R. Tijdeman. *Diophantine Approximation and its Applications*. Springer, 1993.